

DIRECTIONS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF FINANCING THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Annotation: The analysis and conclusions on the directions of increasing the efficiency of financing the education system in our country

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It is known that reforms in the field of education are one of the integral and decisive directions of socio-economic reforms carried out in our country.

It is worth noting that it is necessary to bring our large-scale work in this field, in particular, to the logical conclusion of our national programs on education. For this purpose, the most important task of the relevant ministries and agencies of our Government, as well as the entire educational system, and respected professors and teachers, is to provide thorough education to the young generation, to raise them to be physically and spiritually mature people.

The Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan presented the next budget project for citizens dedicated to the State budget project for 2022. In 2022, it is forecasted that 105503.2 billion sum will be spent on social sector expenses in the state budget, of which education expenses will make up the largest part. Currently, it is expected that about half of the state budget expenses will be allocated to the social sector or 44.5% of the total expenses to the education sector. By 2021, there were 18,345 preschool educational institutions in our country, and by 2022, it is planned to reconstruct and overhaul 22,429 preschool educational institutions and build new preschool educational institutions. The purpose of this is to expand the involvement of children in preschool educational institutions and educate the future generation.

In 2022, 30,823.4 billion will be allocated to finance general education and extracurricular institutions. Sums or total secondary education costs are forecast to increase by 1.18 times.

Extracurricular education includes children's music and art schools and "Barkamol Avlod" schools. It is planned to spend 640.8 billion sum from the state budget for the maintenance of children's music and art schools, and 251.1 billion soums are planned to be allocated from the state budget for the maintenance of "Barkamol Avlod" schools.

In 2022, the main indicators and costs of secondary special professional education will be 802, and 2,222.5 billion sum will be spent from the state budget. It is also planned to allocate 326.2 billion sum from the state budget for academic lyceums in 2022. In 2022, it is planned to allocate 497.6 billion sum from the state budget for vocational colleges, 1,130.3 billion sum from the state budget for vocational schools, 203.0 billion sum from the state budget for technical schools, retraining of personnel in the construction sector we can see that training centers will cost 65.4 billion sum.

It can be seen from this that in the future, the number of professional and academic lyceums will decrease, and the amount of expenses from the state budget will decrease.

From the State budget in 2022 to finance the higher education system It is planned to allocate 5,448.8 billion sum.

To sum up, we can cite as an example the effective organization of financing of the education system, the correct distribution of the state budget, and the control of the expenditures made by the state to budget organizations.

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